

D5.5 Guidelines for validation of ENVRI-FAIR services

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Deliverable abstract

D5.5 “Guidelines for validation of ENVRI-FAIR services” formulates the criteria and test plan for validating the overall quality of the ENVRI-FAIR services and summarises the guidelines for testing and validating the functionality of the services developed in WP8-WP11 in synergy with WP7. The criteria will allow the developers of the ENVRI data services to validate the results towards the EOSC catalogue of services.

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DOCUMENT AMENDMENT PROCEDURE

Amendments, comments, and suggestions should be sent to the Project Manager at manager@envri-fair.eu.

GLOSSARY

A relevant project glossary is included in Appendix A. The latest version of the master list of the glossary is available at <http://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.3465753>.

PROJECT SUMMARY

ENVRI-FAIR is the connection of the ESFRI Cluster of Environmental Research Infrastructures (ENVRI) to the European Open Science Cloud (EOSC). Participating research infrastructures (RI) of the environmental domain cover the subdomains Atmosphere, Marine, Solid Earth and Biodiversity / Ecosystems and thus the Earth system in its full complexity.

The overarching goal is that at the end of the proposed project, all participating RIs have built a set of FAIR data services which enhances the efficiency and productivity of researchers, supports innovation, enables data- and knowledge-based decisions and connects the ENVRI Cluster to the EOSC.

This goal is reached by: (1) well defined community policies and standards on all steps of the data life cycle, aligned with the wider European policies, as well as with international developments; (2) each participating RI will have sustainable, transparent, and auditable data services, for each step of data life cycle, compliant to the FAIR principles. (3) the focus of the proposed work is put on the implementation of prototypes for testing pre-production services at each RI; the catalogue of prepared services is defined for each RI independently, depending on the maturity of the involved RIs; (4) the complete set of thematic data services and tools provided by the ENVRI cluster is exposed under the EOSC catalogue of services.

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1. Introduction

“Guidelines for validation of ENVRI-FAIR services” formulates the criteria and test plan for validating the overall quality of the ENVRI-FAIR services and provides guidelines for testing and validating the functionality of the services developed in WP8-WP11 in synergy with WP7.

The criteria will guide the validation of the ENVRI data services and use cases towards the EOSC catalogue of services when more information will be provided by EOSC.

Section 2 describes the validation at subdomain level, carried out in synergy with WP7. Section 3 describes a method for validating the FAIR service implementation that was used in WP10 but as it springs naturally from the Development Practices, it can be applied to all subdomains with due updates and corrections. Section 4 describes the three most relevant validation criteria used for creating an appropriate level of technical interoperability with the European Open Science Cloud (EOSC).

2. RI Service Validation at the subdomain level

2.1 Test plan for ENVRI services and use cases

This task was progressed in parallel with the work as documented in D7.7 “Test and validation plan of subdomain services” within WP7. This deliverable is related to task 7.4 in which from WP7 side support is offered to guide the subdomains in testing and validating the FAIRness improvements and especially the services that are involved. The four subdomains are at very different stages of maturity and hence testing within their own environments - and therefore testing for ENVRI (i.e., cluster level) services - has to rely on the highest common level of testing available. Of course, it is expected that the level of testing - both unit tests and integration tests - will increase progressively as the subdomains improve their service offerings.

In all subdomains there is a basic level of testing to ensure (a) the accessibility of services, and (b) the expected quality of services. Sub-domain developers are progressively improving the metadata descriptions of the services, although metadata standards differ among the subdomains. The level of documentation also varies among the subdomains. D7.7 has described a structured approach for the tests and, e.g., templates that describe the unit and integration tests for selected use cases, which can be repeated as services evolve in the next releases.

Each subdomain is responsible for the management of its own testing, based on its own governance. In case there are already testing procedures in place then these will be reviewed, documented, and shared with the other subdomains. If there is not yet a structured test process then the test plan and templates, as well as the experiences in other subdomains, will be used as guidelines.

2.2 Cluster level harmonisation criteria

To test the accessibility of service offerings from the subdomains at the cluster level WP5 initiated the development of a prototype ENVRI-Hub: a portal to access the ENVRI catalogue of services and other digital assets, but also the ENVRI knowledge base, training assets and scientific use cases. Here we concentrate on services in the sense of web services.

The testing plan - which is on top of the test and validation plan for services at subdomain and RI level as documented in D7.7 (previous chapter) - is integral to the process of making services available through the ENVRI-Hub. This process - and the criteria used - are described in the Guidelines [section 4] below. The essential validation criteria are:

- (a) the service can be accessed and has an API declared;
- (b) the API and associated metadata are ingested into the ENVRI-Hub catalogue through the ingestion pipeline described in the Guidelines [section 4] below;

- (c) the metadata are validated using SHACL¹ shapes; The intention is to improve progressively the service harmonisation by:
 - (1) improving the metadata schema to allow more attribute values to be populated: this will improve discovery, contextualisation and hence interoperability and re-use of services;
 - (2) improving documentation to assist users in understanding the capabilities of services outside of their own domain and with which they may be unfamiliar.

The relationship of the work on the catalogue and its access from ENVRI-Hub to utilise services, to other elements of the ENVRI-Hub are the subject of current work. In particular, the relationship between the metadata describing services and documentations of the training platform and training catalogue is being discussed, as is the linkage (probably with re-use of metadata) to the ENVRI knowledge base. This ongoing work continues until the end of the ENVRI-FAIR project.

3. A method for validating FAIR service implementation

As described in the previous sections, a harmonisation step was required to create a convergence across the various test plans in the sub-domains and to adopt common guidelines for the testing of the main components of the ENVRI Hub. Given the considerable number of key players i.e., many RIs in 4 different sub-domains, a similar approach was also adopted for finding common criteria for the validation of the FAIR services produced within the sub-domain RIs.

The method largely leverages on the methodology described in Bailo et al., 2019. The founding concept is straightforward: take as a common basis the Software Development Life Cycle (SDLC) that is common to all RIs - and more generally to all those producing software for creating services for data stewardship - and define where in SDLC some FAIR activities are needed to promote convergence towards FAIR services.

FAIR validation steps and Software Development Life Cycle (SDLC) processes are shown in parallel in Figure 1, and correspondences between the two are highlighted. FAIR validation can be described as a three-step process: the first step (A) represents a method for analysing FAIR principles and providing an evaluation with respect to the existing landscape; Figure 1 presents the four-stages adoption roadmap (Bailo, 2019), but this step can be replaced by any of the many existing methods or Matrix for evaluating the FAIR principles (e.g., Fair Implementation Profiles (Schultes et al., 2020) or the FAIR Data Maturity Model (Bahim et al., 2020)); the second step (B) is devoted to the evaluation and gap analysis to make emerge the priority by which FAIR principles at each stage need to be addressed; the third step (C) is devoted, on the basis of the gap analysis, to the selection of technical activities to undertake, and then to actual implementation.

What emerges is that steps one and two of the FAIR adoption processes are carried out in the Analysis Phase in the SDLC; indeed, FAIR principles are elicited as requirements and gap analysis to understand which ones will be implemented at each “round” of implementation is performed. Phases from design to operation are executed in the “technical activities” step of the FAIR adoption process.

¹ SHACL Shapes Constraint Language, a language for validating RDF graphs against a set of conditions: <https://www.w3.org/TR/shacl/>

Figure 1: Software Development Life Cycle Process (SDLC) (bottom) and FAIRness methodology (top) in comparison.

The three steps (a, b and c) described in Figure 1 are already considered and encompassed in ENVRI-FAIR. Starting with the FAIRness evaluation of the ENVRI, the Task 5.1 leaders together with the subdomains and with help from WP7 organised the first round of the FAIRness assessment which has been reported in D5.1 “Requirement analysis, technology review and gap analysis of environmental RIs” (Magagna et al., 2020). This task provided an up-to-date gap analysis (step B in Figure 1) of the most common gaps the ENVRI needed to bridge with respect to the FAIR principles but also reviewing the EOSC requirements and their impact on the RIs. Following the FAIRness assessment an implementation plan for the cluster (step C shown in Figure 1), based on the common development targets defined in the gap analysis, was prepared by WP5 (D5.2 “Implementation Plan for Common Development Goals”, Adamaki and Vermeulen, 2020). Recently, with guidance from ENVRI-FAIR partners involved in the GO FAIR project, the ENVRI worked on their FAIR Implementation Profiles (FIPs; Schultes et al., 2020) which capture the FAIR implementation choices made by the RIs. As explained by the authors in Schultes et al. (2020) the collection of FIPs from the RIs can compose a Convergence Matrix for the community of RIs participating in the exercise, aiming to track the evolving landscape of the FAIR implementations. This methodology contributes significantly to the first part of the FAIR Adoption process illustrated in Figure 1.

Steps a) and b) are more recently covered by the FAIR Implementation Profiles (FIP) work conducted by Barbara Magagna within WP7 and coordinated with the Go-FAIR Project [FIP]. Step c) is exactly where the harmonization of test plans described above comes, to find a convergence for the testing of the various services and, at the same time, define specific technical activities for the services to be tested.

4. Guidelines for integration within ENVRI-EOSC catalogue of services

One of the goals of ENVRI-FAIR is to create an appropriate level of technical interoperability with the European Open Science Cloud (EOSC). To achieve this objective, it was agreed in the context of WP5 Task Force 1 to implement a metadata catalogue schema and associated management services, with the aim of describing and providing access to assets available from the ENVRI. To be used as ENVRI Catalogue in the framework of EOSC, appropriate transformations are required to match EOSC requirements. All details are reported in the Task Force 1 overview document (Bailo et al., 2022).

A first prototype of the catalogue has been produced (see Figure 2). It is built based on the EPOS approach, i.e., implementing a rich metadata catalogue. The machine actionable catalogue web-APIs are available at:

<https://ics-c.epos-ip.org/demo/k8s-epos-deploy/envri-fair-catalogue/api/webapi/v1.3/swagger-ui/> while the catalogue portal (for humans) is currently available here <https://hubtest.envri-fair.eu/>.

Figure 2: Screenshot of the ENVRI-Hub catalogue of services

Guidelines for integration were either provided or discussed with the Key stakeholders. Such guidelines also provide clear criteria for the integration of asset descriptions from the cluster RIs.

As of 1st of April 2022, the catalogue contains 28 entries. These are provided by Research Infrastructures that volunteered to participate in the ENVRI-FAIR catalogue proof of concepts by means of a rich metadata description done with the EPOS-DCAT-AP extension (<https://github.com/epos-eu/EPOS-DCAT-AP>). Such metadata descriptions are then ingested into the catalogue by means of a so-called “ingestion pipeline”, i.e., a procedure that validates syntax and semantics of the provided metadata, also through SHACL shapes, thus improving the quality of the metadata.

Rich metadata is fundamental for being able to share assets with external initiatives, so the first guideline addresses a criterion that can be described as follows:

1st Criterion for integration within the ENVRI Catalogue of Services

All services included in the catalogue need to be described by means of rich metadata (some details e.g., what standards, schema etc).

Being it a first round to test the feasibility of the catalogue, heterogeneous assets were included. However, the different types of assets need to be categorized, which leads us to defining the second criterion:

2nd Criterion for integration within the ENVRI Catalogue of Services

Provide a clear definition of the types of assets to be included in the catalogue.

Applying this criterion ensures that any potential consumers of the catalogue will be able to understand whether the assets consumed are machine-actionable or human-readable.

Other criteria are related to the compliance of assets to the FAIR principles, which include several key criteria like the adoption of Persistent Identifiers, Authentication and Authorization Infrastructure in place and others. Such criteria are still under development, but they can be summarized as follows:

3rd Criterion for integration within the ENVRI Catalogue of Services

Ensure that the assets provided and described in the catalogue are tested, validated and compliant to the FAIR principles.

The above criteria will ensure that the assets included in the catalogue are validated with an adequate level of robustness and richness in terms of metadata description, so that these can be easily interoperated with the EOSC catalogue.

5. Conclusion

The current deliverable describes the Guidelines for validation of ENVRI-FAIR services. It addresses firstly the RI Service Validation at subdomain level carried out by and in synergy with WP7. It was a twofold activity that encompassed both a specific action for each subdomain, by outlining a Test plan for ENVRI services and use cases, and common action for studying and possibly defining Cluster level harmonisation criteria. Then, a generic methodology for assessing the FAIRness of the provided services is described, as used fully in WP10 and partially by other sub-domains. The methodology brings together already existing practices and methods from the communities and can be considered an evolution towards FAIR of the activities already in place in the sub-domains. Based on such a methodology and based on the work carried out by WP7, guidelines for integration within ENVRI Catalogue of Services are described. These guidelines are in line with the work done either in ENVRI-FAIR subdomains, but also with the work done in the WP5 Task Forces. The criteria will ensure that the assets included in the catalogue are validated with an adequate level of robustness and richness in terms of metadata description so that these can be easily interoperate with the EOSC catalogue.

6. References

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Annex A - Glossary

AAAI: Authentication, Authorisation, and Accounting Infrastructure
CERIF: Common European Research Information Format
DCAT: Data Catalog Vocabulary
EPOS-DCAT-AP: DCAT Application Profile for EPOS
DDSS: Data, Data products, Software and Services
DIAS: Data and Information Access Services
EOSC: European Open Science Cloud
EPOS Strategic Plan: Defines the activities of EPOS-ERIC
GEP: Geohazards Exploitation Platform
ICS-C: Integrated Core Services - Central Hub
ICS-D: Distributed Integrated Core Services Distributed
PID: Persistent Identifier
SDLC: Software Development Life Cycle
SHACL: Shapes Constraint Language
TCS: Thematic Core Services